

STUDIES ON FERRI-PHOSPHORIC ACID COMPLEXES

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Ferri-phosphoric acid system has been studied in solution by different physico-chemical methods. Two complex ions have been detected and formulated as $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_2^-$.

Ferric iron forms complex ions with phosphoric acid as is shown by the disappearance of colour, lowering of oxidation potential, inability to liberate iodine from potassium iodide, etc. The use of phosphoric acid to convert ferric ion into a complex is also well known, but the number of complex ions formed and their nature have not been definitely established. Ricca and Meduri (*Gazzetta*, 1934, 64, 235) from conductometric measurements of ferric chloride-phosphoric acid mixtures have obtained a maxima at 1:1, and have formulated the compound as $\text{H}_3[\text{Cl}_3\text{FePO}_4]$, but Jensen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 221, 1) has shown that the complex formed is purely a phosphato complex and not a mixed chloro-phosphato complex. The same compound has also been detected by Lanford and Samuel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 291) by applying Job's method of continued variation in ferric nitrate-phosphoric acid mixtures employing thiocyanate solution for colorimetric determination of ferric ion. The formula of the imperfect complex has been established as $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)^+$; and from the study of the equilibrium the same workers have determined the dissociation constant of the complex ion using thiocyanate as the indicator for free ferric ion.

Babko and Kodenskaya (*Compt. rend. Acad. Sci. U.S.S.R.*, 1946, 52, 37; *J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1946, 16, 1549; 1947, 17, 1080) as also Chatterjee (*Science & Culture*, 1949, 16, 201) have shown that in ferric-thiocyanate system in aqueous solution there is a dynamic equilibrium between the reactant ions and as many as five different complex ions: $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})^{++}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})_2^+$, $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})_4^-$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{SCN})_5^{--}$, the formation of which will disturb the equilibrium between ferric ion and phosphoric acid when thiocyanate is used for the determination of free ferric ion in equilibrium. Moreover, the measured intensity of the red colour formed is due to the total contribution of all the five ferri-thiocyanate complexes, the individual contributions of each of which are not known. But the individual concentrations of these ferri-thiocyanate complexes will vary with the varying concentration of the reactants which actually happens in the case under consideration. Further, the colour gradually fades away with time, and hence, the use of thiocyanate for the determination of the concentration of free ferric ion in equilibrium cannot be recommended. In the present investigation attempts have been made to study the ferri-phosphoric acid system by different physico-chemical methods such as thermometric, conductometric, colorimetric and modified transport experiments to detect the complex ions formed. Two phosphato complexes have been detected, containing ferric: phosphate in the ratio of 1:1 and 1:2, which have been formulated as $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_2^-$.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The stock solutions were prepared by dissolving AnalaR quality ferric chloride and phosphoric acid in water. The ferric chloride solution was standardised against dichromate using diphenylamine as an indicator, and the phosphoric acid solution standardised against alkali using a mixture of two parts of phenolphthalein and one part of α -naphtholphthalein (p_n 9.6) as the indicator.

Thermometric Titration

The arrangement for the thermometric titration is the same as has been previously described by Haldar (this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 157). Both phosphoric acid and ferric chloride were alternately used as the titre.

TABLE I

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 1 M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 5M.
 FeCl_3 taken = 40 c.c. (cf. Fig. 1).

H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.190°	0.000	7 c.c.	1.675°	1.515	13 c.c.	1.200°	1.990
1	2.950°	0.240	8	1.540°	1.650	14	1.180°	2.010
2	2.695°	0.495	9	1.425°	1.765	15	1.175°	2.015
3	2.450°	0.740	10	1.345°	1.845	16	1.175°	2.015
4	2.225°	0.965	11	1.280°	1.910	17	1.175°	2.015
5	2.025°	1.165	12	1.230°	1.960	18	1.175°	2.015
6	1.840°	1.350				19	1.175°	2.015

TABLE II

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 0.5M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 2.5M.
 FeCl_3 taken = 40 c.c. (cf. Fig. 2).

H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.875°	0.000°	7 c.c.	4.360°	0.515°	13 c.c.	4.215°	0.660°
1	4.805	0.070	8	4.315	0.560	14	4.210	0.665
2	4.725	0.150	9	4.280	0.595	15	4.205	0.670
3	4.640	0.235	10	4.250	0.625	16	4.200	0.675
4	4.560	0.315	11	4.235	0.640	17	4.200	0.675
5	4.480	0.395	12	4.225	0.650	18	4.200	0.675
6	4.440	0.455				19	4.200	0.675

TABLE III

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 0.5M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 5M.
 FeCl_3 taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 3)

H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	H_3PO_4 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.330°	0.000°	4 c.c.	2.400°	0.930°	8 c.c.	2.050	1.280°
0.5	3.215	0.115	4.5	2.320	1.010	8.5	2.025	1.305
1	3.080	0.250	5	2.260	1.070	9	2.000	1.330
1.5	2.945	0.385	5.5	2.205	1.125	9.5	1.980	1.350
2	2.810	0.520	6	2.165	1.165	10	1.960	1.370
2.5	2.700	0.630	6.5	2.130	1.200	10.5	1.940	1.390
3	2.580	0.750	7	2.100	1.230	11	1.920	1.410
3.5	2.485	0.845	7.5	2.070	1.260			

TABLE IV

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 2M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 1M.
 H_3PO_4 taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 4).

FeCl_3 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	FeCl_3 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.	FeCl_3 added.	Temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.170°	0.000°	9 c.c.	2.410°	1.760°	17 c.c.	1.520°	2.650°
1	3.970	0.200	10	2.250	1.920	18	1.460	2.710
2	3.745	0.425	11	2.110	2.060	19	1.415	2.755
3	3.520	0.650	12	1.980	2.190	20	1.370	2.800
4	3.310	0.860	13	1.875	2.295	21	1.330	2.840
5	3.110	1.060	14	1.770	2.400	22	1.295	2.875
6	2.920	1.250	15	1.670	2.500	23	1.265	2.905
7	2.740	1.430	16	1.590	2.580	24	1.235	2.935
8	2.570	1.600						

Conductometric Methods

A dilute solution of ferric chloride was titrated conductometrically against a concentrated solution of phosphoric acid. In the arrangement for the determination of conductivity the principle of Wheatstone bridge was employed. The alternate current was supplied by a valve oscillator of the Hartley type giving an accurately determined frequency, free from harmonics. The sharpness of the minima was enhanced by a vacuum tube amplifier, the telephone being connected to the plate-circuit of the vacuum tube. Solutions for all conductivity experiments were prepared in twice distilled water and the conductivity cell was kept in an electrically controlled thermostat.

Conductivity measurements were also carried out in various solutions of ferric chloride, phosphoric acid and equimolecular mixtures of ferric chloride and phosphoric

acid to determine the formula of the complex formed by employing Job's method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) of continued variation. The difference in the conductivity of the mixture from the additive conductivity of the individual reactants was plotted to get the composition corresponding to the maximum complex formation.

TABLE V

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 0.01M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 1.2832M.
 FeCl_3 taken = 50 c.c. Temp. = 27 ± 0.1 . (Fig 5).

H_3PO_4 added (c.c.)	0.00	0.12	0.24	0.36	0.48	0.60	0.72	0.84	0.96	1.08	1.20	1.32	1.44
$\frac{1}{R} \times 10^3$ (ohms)	11.11	16.03	21.74	26.53	28.57	30.21	31.35	31.95	33.00	33.44	33.90	34.84	35.46

TABLE VI

Conductometric measurements.

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 0.04M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 0.04M. Temp. = $27 \pm 0.1^\circ$. (Fig. 6).

Conductivity of H_3PO_4 .		Conductivity of FeCl_3 .		Conductivity of the mixture.		Difference.
H_3PO_4 . 10 c.c.	Water. $1/R_1 \times 10^3$.	FeCl_3 . 90 c.c.	Water. $1/R_2 \times 10^3$.	H_3PO_4 . 10 c.c.	FeCl_3 . 90 c.c.	$[1/R_3 - (1/R_1 + 1/R_2)] \times 10^3$.
10	6.48	139.86	10	155.04	8.70	
20	10.85	133.33	20	158.73	14.55	
30	14.54	125.00	30	161.29	21.75	
40	17.63	99.01	40	158.73	41.09	
50	20.53	83.68	50	153.85	49.64	
53	21.05	80.65	53	149.25	47.55	
56	21.86	75.19	56	142.86	45.31	
60	22.86	69.44	60	133.33	41.03	
63	23.72	64.52	63	126.58	38.34	
65	24.27	61.73	65	120.48	34.48	
67	24.66	58.82	67	115.61	32.13	
70	25.22	54.64	70	107.53	27.67	
72	25.91	51.02	72	102.04	25.11	
75	26.46	46.30	75	93.90	21.14	
80	27.86	38.46	80	80.00	13.68	
90	30.03	21.14	90	54.05	2.88	

Colorimetric Titration

The colour of the free ferric ion is a suitable property to follow the progress of the reaction by colorimetric titration, as the colour gradually disappears with the addition of phosphoric acid. The percentage of light transmitted through ferric chloride solution was measured with Lumetron Photoelectric colorimeter, model 400G, of Photovolt Corporation, New York; and then the percentage readings were converted into optical density. The arrangement and the method of measurements are the same as has been described in a previous paper of the author (Haldar and Banerjee, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1948, 14, 1). Distilled water was used as the standard and measurements were taken at wave-length of 490 m μ .

TABLE VII

Conc. of FeCl_3 soln. = 0.1M. Conc. of H_3PO_4 soln. = 5M. FeCl_3 taken = 20 c.c.

H_3PO_4 added.	Opt. $D \times 10^3$.	H_3PO_4 added.	Opt. $D \times 10^3$.	H_3PO_4 added.	Opt. $D \times 10^3$.
0.00 c.c.	80.97	0.25 c.c.	35.65	0.50 c.c.	16.75
0.05	63.83	0.30	31.88	0.55	14.27
0.10	53.76	0.35	27.57	0.60	11.35
0.15	46.85	0.40	23.46	0.65	9.06
0.20	41.02	0.45	20.07	0.70	8.35

Transport Experiments

Transport experiments were carried out to determine the nature of the charge of the complexes formed. The transport apparatus used is due to Clement and Duval (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1938, v. 5, 1020). The base of the apparatus was filled with a mixture containing ferric chloride and excess of phosphoric acid. The limbs above the stoppers were filled with potassium chloride solution and connected to a source of 105 volts D.C., through platinum wires, and electrolysed for half-an-hour. The potassium chloride solution from the anode compartment, when tested with potassium ferrocyanide, gave definite indication of ferric radical. The experiment was again repeated with a mixture of ferric chloride and phosphoric acid in the ratio of 1:1; and the solution from the cathode compartment, when tested with ammonium molybdate, indicated the presence of phosphate. Blank experiments were carried out in each case under identical conditions but without passing electric current and the solutions from the anode and the cathode compartments were found free from ferric and phosphate radicals.

DISCUSSION

In the thermometric titration curves (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) obtained by direct titrations, three breaks appear at the points corresponding to ferric chloride: phosphoric acid

FIG. 1

[Table I: M- FeCl_3 and 5M- H_3PO_4]

FIG. 2

[Table II: 0.5 M- FeCl_3 and 2.5 M- H_3PO_4]

FIG. 3

[Table III: 0.5 M-FeCl₃ and 5M-H₃PO₄]

FIG. 4

[Table IV: 2M-FeCl₃ and M-H₃PO₄]

FIG. 5

25 32.5 50 65 75 100
 Drops of H₃PO₄ → 100 drops of H₃PO₄ = 1.2c.c.
 [Table V: 0.01M-FeCl₃ and 1.2832M-H₃PO₄]

in the ratio of 1 : 1, 2 : 3 and 1 : 2. The break corresponding to Fe⁺⁺⁺ : H₃PO₄ = 2 : 3 may be due to a mixture of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 and so may not represent a new compound formation. The curve (Fig. 4) in the reverse titration, *i.e.*, when ferric chloride has been used as the titre shows all the breaks as in the direct titrations.

The conductometric titration curve (Fig. 5) shows two breaks at ferric : phosphate = 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, confirming the results of thermometric titrations. In this curve no break corresponding to the compound ferric : phosphate = 2 : 3 is observed and so the breaks in the thermometric titration curves corresponding to this point do not represent true compound formation.

In the Job's method of continued variation, when the difference in conductivity is plotted against the volume of ferric chloride, a sharp maxima is obtained (Fig. 6) at

50 c.c. of ferric chloride corresponding to the point ferric : phosphoric acid equal to 1 : 1, but there is no indication of the other compound containing ferric and phosphoric

FIG. 6

[Table VI: 0.04 M-FeCl₃+0.04 M-H₃PO₄]

FIG. 7

[Table VII: 0.1 M-FeCl₃+5M-H₃PO₄]

acid in the ratio of 1 : 2. It has been shown by Job himself that in the case of more than one compound formation, indications are obtained for all the compounds only under the most favourable conditions. The colorimetric titration curve (Fig. 7) also shows a sharp break at the point 1 : 1 excluding the first point.

Thus, the compounds containing ferric : phosphoric acid = 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 are indicated by various methods within the range of 0.01M to 1M solutions of ferric chloride and are therefore sufficiently established.

The presence of phosphate radical in the cathode compartment in the 1 : 1 mixture of ferric chloride and phosphoric acid, as shown by the transport experiment, indicates that the phosphato complex of the above composition is positively charged, and hence, may be formulated as $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)^+$. This is in agreement with the formulation suggested by Lanford and Samuel (*loc. cit.*). The formulation as chloro-phosphato complex $\text{H}_2[\text{Cl}_2\text{FePO}_4]$ by Ricca and Meduri (*loc. cit.*) cannot explain the presence of phosphate radical in the cathode compartment, and is therefore untenable. On the same basis the other complex ion containing ferric : phosphoric acid in the ratio of 1 : 2 may be formulated as $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_2^-$, which indicates that iron should migrate to the anode during transport experiment and is actually found to be so. If the number of hydrogen atoms in the complex forming phosphate radical be assumed to be other than one, the nature of the charge of the complex ions will be changed, and the assumption cannot explain the results of the transport experiment. If, for example, the complex forming phosphato radical be $(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^-$ the complex ions will be $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)^{++}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2^{\frac{1}{2}-}$, in which case the presence of iron in anode compartment cannot be explained.

Thus, in a solution containing excess of phosphoric acid and ferric ion, two complex ions, $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)^+$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{HPO}_4)_2^-$ are formed according to the reactions :

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